

Geometric Model of a Deepwater with a Complex Surface Working Organ

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 28 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 27 Nov 2024; **Published:** 18 Dec 2024

Abstract: A significant economic effect can be achieved by creating technical means designed to reduce costs while simultaneously cultivating high-quality and high-yield agricultural crops in farming conditions, as well as using them in production. In improving the reclamation status of lands, that is, in substantiating deep loosening working bodies for loosening gypsum soils, it is important to study the shape of the side profile of their working column.

Keywords: deep softener, spline, geometric model, aggregate, crushed farm, linear-discrete.

Introduction.

From a design perspective, the methods of transitioning from graphical representation of the surface of the ripper for working parts of agricultural machinery units to mathematical (and vice versa) should be simple, i.e., understandable and universal for a wide range of users. In this regard, we will consider methods for describing complex surfaces, including loosening surfaces, with non-high-level splines, in particular, parabolic and cubic, with interpolating values of the function and its derivatives not only in nodes, but also on grid lines, while adhering to the conditions of smoothness relative to a given linear-discrete frame. The process of building such splines is much easier than the process of building high-level splines. In mechanical engineering design, particularly in the design of agricultural machinery units, one of the most logically precise stages of design activity is the design of agricultural machinery structures and working units. Therefore, it is no coincidence that computer technology is being implemented in mechanical engineering, combining agricultural machinery with engineering calculations. In the design process, a person typically works not with an object, but only with its image - a geometric model. This allows the experiments to be conducted not during the plowing process, but on expensive and labor-intensive land, rather than on a drawing. The presence of a geometric model (graphic model), as well as the visualization of the object (aggregate) as a whole until it is ready, allows for the best connection of all parts (algorithms) into a single whole. The foundation of technical forms, such as machine parts, aggregates, deep looseners, etc., that have emerged in the last few decades, is made up of curved surfaces and slopes (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The geometric surface of the deep softener of the working body with a complex surface.

These forms are distinguished by their technological, functional, constructive, and economic advantages. In the design and construction of modern, newly invented shapes, the geometric model (stage) of design plays a significant role, as the surface must satisfy predetermined conditions. One of the important stages in the design of a deep loosening device with a complex surface is the geometric design of its middle surface, i.e., the determination of the geometric shape of the loosening process, which loosens the soil profile and best meets agrotechnical requirements. It is usually possible to obtain a partial or complete geometric interpretation of such requirements. In such cases, their consideration in surface design reduces to solving geometric problems.

In the practice of designing a deep loosening machine for a working body with a complex surface, taking into account complex surfaces, the problem of determining the coordinates of a set of discrete points on the surface of the aggregate ripper often arises, for example: when calculating the ripper in the working or stationary state, it is necessary to mark the middle surface with a pointed frame along the specified grid in the plan; when controlling the shape of the ripper being constructed, it is necessary to know the coordinates of the control points on the surface. For complex surfaces, it takes a lot of work to solve. Often, the surface is plotted in the form of an arbitrary grid dot frame.

However, in many cases, when solving engineering tasks related to the design, calculation, and manufacture of aggregates, a situation arises where a given network is not acceptable as a base network in relation to the number of rippers. In this case, the designer faces the task of transforming the initial frame into a new one, including special lines (geodesic, asymptotic, various Gaussian curves, Frane moduli, etc.). For example, existing algorithms for constructing a broken geodesic line passing through two points on the surface of the frame allow for the construction of geodesic frames that connect pairs of points on a given surface by sequentially selecting initial parameters, as well as a ripper (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Construction of a complex geometric surface of the ripper's working body.

However, a significant drawback of such frames is that they are extremely regular, and for engineering purposes, as a rule, the task arises of studying geometric structures characterized by an ordered frame. In this regard, a spline-approximation algorithm [1,2] was introduced into the software algorithm complex that implements the task of frame replication. This allows obtaining a regular linear (or pointed) frame of the surface (softener), which in turn minimizes the size of the initial data, facilitates the creation of computer-based data processing and display algorithms, and also allows for the use of the developed software package. The process of designing a ripper shape can be called a rather complex information and computational complex, directly related to the researcher's intellectual activity.

Analyzing this activity within the framework of a real system for designing a loosening form, it is possible to distinguish the following stages of design work.

1. Study of the technical assignment (design assignment);
2. Selection of a constructive solution;
3. Defining technical (geometric, strength, etc.) and economic calculations;
4. Perform drawing and graphic works on modern computers and SAPR subsystems.

About half of the designers' working hours are spent on purely technical work that can be automated, therefore there is a need to identify these works and take measures to ensure their automation.

There are three main areas where this problem can be solved:

- ✓ rationalization (optimization) of design systems;
- ✓ improvement of the designer's working conditions;
- ✓ comprehensive automation of the designer's non-creative functions in the design process.

Due to the rapid development and application of mathematical methods and tools in computer technology, the most promising direction is the design of surfaces, shaping, and comprehensive automation of geometry description, which can be conditionally divided into two main classes.

1. The formation and description of the geometric configuration of surfaces and the solution of a complex of applied problems in them (technical, economic calculations, phase approximation and discretization, construction of surface networks, solution of differential, metric and positional problems).
2. Reflecting input, output, and intermediate data in the form of drawings, graphs, and tables at different stages. Methods for solving computer-oriented problems are understood as a

synthesis of methods of analytical and differential geometry, computer modeling of graphic methods, and methods of approximation. The choice of technologies is determined by the setting of a specific task.

When creating a mathematical model of mold formation that performs the function of a ripper, it is necessary not only to control the shape of the ripper shell, but also to provide a form that is sufficiently simple and user-friendly (due to soil resistance) for a computer to describe its surface (geometric structures, algebraic, piecewise-analytical, kinematic, frame), thus, within the framework of automated design, two main tasks can be solved: requirements are placed that fully reflect the geometric essence of the structures. Solving these problems provides solutions to many other problems of applied geometry of surfaces, such as:

- ✓ determining an arbitrary point of the surface;
- ✓ construction of differential characteristics of the surface at a given point;
- ✓ construction of surface sections with arbitrary planes;
- ✓ construction of an arbitrary surface frame;
- ✓ surface shape control.

Methods for describing surfaces have been proposed for the case of a generalized Hermite spline constructed on a curvilinear grid, where the grid is represented by two families of straight lines and curves, and a transition through a fractional-rational spline, which allows for the construction of a mathematical model of the surface of a pointed frame without pre-reflection on a rectangular grid.

Conclusion. To apply theoretical research in practice, field experimental samples of a working body with a complex surface were created, and field trials were successfully conducted on the fields of the "Uktam Kayum" farm in the Gijduvan district (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Field trials of a soil softener with a working organ with a complex surface.

During the experiments, the working body with a complex surface was installed in the lower part of the working body of the deep loosening device with a complex surface using special chains, the diameter of the working body with a complex surface was $D_{ms}=0.15-0.20$ m, the

length of the working body with a complex surface was $L_{ms}=0.20-0.25$ m, the length of the chain was $L_{zu}=0.25-0.30$ m, the depth of processing of the working body was $H_{ich}=0.55-0.65$ m, the distance between the working bodies was $M_{oj}=0.50-0.70$, the transverse distance of the working bodies is $M_{kj}=0.70$ m and the processing speed of the unit is $V=6-8$ km/h, in the front lower part of the working body columns $n_d=3$ wave-like rippers with a coverage width of $d_t=0.09$ m are installed, in the rear lower part of the working body columns, working bodies with a complex surface are installed through a chain of $n_{ms}=3$ pieces, breaking the soil, creating rotational motion on the surface of the working bodies with a complex surface due to the movement of the soil during [3,4].

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